

MULTIPOINT CONVERTER DESIGN AND OPTIMAL LOCATION IN DISTRIBUTION GRIDS

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Abstract

Multipoint converters (MPC) are presented as a general power electronics solution that can contribute to facilitate a massive integration of distributed renewable generation while enhancing the interconnection of multiple electrical grids and equipment. The MPC implement an integrated solution combining the advantages of energy storage and other grid support equipment. This paper presents an optimisation-based methodology to size and allocate multipoint power converters together with a techno-economic comparison to other conventional approaches. This methodology includes AC power flow constraints and is evaluated in a case study based on IEEE 33 bus system to identify the best scenarios where multipoint converters can be considered as a potential solution.

1 Introduction

The increasing penetration of renewable energy sources is transforming the conventional design and operation of the low and medium-voltage grid and is leading to some technical challenges related to overloads, voltage regulation, fault levels or power quality issues [1]. Solutions to increase the distributed energy resources (DER) hosting capacity include grid reinforcement with new lines and substations or with new equipment [2].

Power electronics components have an important role in improving the operation of the distribution grid. In particular, Voltage Source Converters (VSC) provide active and reactive power control to reduce overloads and regulate voltages. Soft Open Points (SOP) are presented in the literature as a solution to connect and reconfigure feeders of the distribution grid. Power controllability and firewall capacity against faults are the main advantages of SOP compared to a simple switch [3–5].

The multipoint converter (MPC) is presented as a general power electronics solution, that represents an improvement of the SOP concept combined with several terminals and functionalities. The MPC can integrate multiple ports with AC and DC outputs, which could be used to introduce storage, DC loads or AC feeders. The MPC is expected to provide additional services for AC and DC systems using the support of battery storage, for example, frequency support. Moreover, the introduction of multipoint converters improves flexibility and controllability, as well as resilience by enabling islanding operation and black-start capabilities. In general, the MPC design and services are different for LV and MV distribution grids [6].

Multipoint converters can facilitate a massive integration of distributed renewable generation while enhancing the interconnection of multiple electrical grids and equipment in AC or DC and considers different voltage or frequency levels. The MPC implement an integrated solution combining the

advantages of energy storage and other grid support equipment. Therefore, the overall number of power electronics can be reduced. The additional investment required to install multipoint converters must be compensated with income from provided services and additional generation that is curtailed due to grid operation constraints [6].

Reconfiguration of the distribution network or the optimal new topology is widely studied in the literature. Typically, the objective is to minimize the costs and network losses, and radial network operation is ensured. Traditionally, only lines and switches were considered. For example, [7] presents a mixed integer linear programming (MILP) that includes DC power flow. An improvement of this approach is presented in [8], where geographic information system (GIS) is applied. [9] presents a model based on the non-convex optimal power flow (OPF) with binary variables that define if each line is switched on or off. However, new methods also include power electronics. In [4], the system operation with Soft Normally-Open Points (SNOPs) is simulated in different placements, but SNOP ratings are set previously and current level constraints are not considered. Also, [10] and [11] determine the size and allocation of SOPs with a relaxed optimal power flow (OPF) with costs minimisation, using the second-order cone programming (SOCP) approach where voltage and current angles are eliminated from the power flow model to make it convex.

This paper analyses and evaluates how multipoint converters can improve distribution grids operation. In particular, the contribution of this paper is an optimization-based methodology, which includes AC power flow constraints, to size [6] and allocate the multipoint converter. The methodology is validated in a case study adapted from the IEEE 33 bus system. Then, general conclusions are obtained about the potential application and feasibility of multipoint converters to improve distributed generation integration in distribution grids.

2 Methodology

This section presents a methodology to size and allocate multiport converters used to interconnect MV feeders.

Several representative days are considered, as full-year optimisation has high computational requirements. Multiport converter sizing is determined with an optimization-based methodology [6].

Several configurations are simulated to find the best location. A configuration is defined by the location of the multiport converters and switches. Then, the multiport converter sizing optimization is performed for each configuration separately. Comparing the results of the different configurations, the configuration with lower objective function value is the optimal.

Generation and demand profiles with hourly resolution are provided for different representative days. Technical parameters of the grid and assets included in the system are also needed. Moreover, cost parameters of the grid reinforcements must be provided. As a result, several economical and technical indicators are obtained to evaluate the advantages of installing a multiport converter. These indicators can be also employed to compare different interconnection configurations.

2.1 Multiport converter sizing

The nominal power of the multiport converter terminals is determined with an optimisation that considers hourly load and generation profiles and the grid constraints. Optimal system operation and some indicators are also obtained. Different elements can be included in the optimisation: the grid, loads, generators, and multiport converter. For each day, the proposed optimisation considers a separate sub-model with all system components. The sizing variables must be common on all days and energetic indicators that represent the whole year are supposed to be the weighted sum for the representative days [6].

2.1.1 Objective function

The multiport converter is introduced to improve feeders' operation without an excessive additional cost. The optimisation will minimise the multiport converter cost while optimising other indicators depending on the case study.

This methodology can be applied to a wide range of scenarios. In this paper, the objective of the multiport converter is to avoid undervoltages and reduce power losses in the lines. Therefore, the optimisation will minimise the losses.

As a result, the objective function can be expressed as:

$$[\min] C_{MPC} - E_{loss} \cdot C_{loss} \cdot t_{life} \quad (1)$$

where C_{MPC} is the multiport converter cost, E_{loss} is the annual losses, C_{loss} is the cost of the losses, supposed as 50 €/kW, and t_{life} is a factor to weight the two main terms supposed as 20 years, which is similar to the multiport converter lifetime. The expressions of C_{MPC} and E_{loss} are presented in Section 2.1.3 and 2.1.5 respectively.

2.1.2 Grid model

Grid variables are related to its operation. Therefore, they are defined for each electrical node and for each hour of the considered representative days. Grid variables include active and reactive power injected, voltage phase and magnitude, and line current.

The grid constraints are related to:

- Voltage magnitude limits, supposed as $\pm 10\%$ of the nominal value.
- The main grid is supposed to be the slack. Therefore, the voltage magnitude and angle of the main grid node are fixed at 1 p.u. and 0° respectively.
- AC power flow equations to ensure active and reactive power balance.
- Line current limits. The current of each line is calculated and its maximum value is limited.

Additionally, to connect the other elements to the grid, active and reactive power balance must be done for each bus.

2.1.3 Multiport converter model

Multiport converter variables are related to both the operation and sizing of the converter. Operation variables are defined for each multiport converter terminal k connected to the node i for each hour t of the considered representative days d . They include the active and reactive powers exchanged by the multiport converter terminal, $p_{MPC-k,i,t,d}$ and $q_{MPC-k,i,t,d}$. On the other hand, this sizing variable is the nominal power of each multiport converter terminal connected to the node i ($s_{n,MPC-k,i}$). This variable is expressed as the maximum apparent power considering all hourly powers exchanged by the converter terminal. All these variables are expressed per unit.

The multiport converter constraints are related to:

- Multiport converter power balance. This must be ensured considering active powers exchanged by each converter terminal, including if a centralised generator is introduced as an additional terminal of the MPC. Therefore, active power balance within a multiport converter is expressed as:

$$\sum_{k,i} p_{MPC-k,i,t,d} = 0 \quad \forall t, d \quad (2)$$

- Multiport current limits, which are expressed as:

$$p_{MPC-k,i,t,d}^2 + q_{MPC-k,i,t,d}^2 \leq (v_{i,t,d} \cdot i_{max,MPC-k,i})^2 \quad \forall k, i, t, d \quad (3)$$

$$i_{max,MPC-k,i} = \frac{s_{n,MPC-k,i}}{v_{n-i}} \quad \forall k, i \quad (4)$$

where $v_{i,t,d}$ is the voltage of the bus i at time t, d , and v_{n-i} is the nominal voltage of the bus i .

- Reactive power limits. It has been limited the reactive power exchanged by the multiport according to IEEE Standard 1547 [12], which defines a minimum capability of $\pm 44\%$ for distributed energy storage, corresponding to a power factor of 0.915. Therefore, the reactive power limits are expressed as:

$$q_{MPC-k,i,t,d} \leq 0.44 \cdot s_{n,MPC-k,i} \quad \forall k, i, t, d \quad (5)$$

$$-q_{MPC-k,i,t,d} \leq 0.44 \cdot s_{n,MPC-k,i} \quad \forall k, i, t, d \quad (6)$$

- Cost of the multiport converter, expressed as:

$$C_{MPC} = \sum_{k,i} C_{conv-k} \cdot s_{n,MPC-k,i} \cdot S_b \quad (7)$$

where C_{conv-k} is the unitary cost of the multiport converter terminal k , supposed as 150 €/kVA [13].

2.1.4 Generator model

The generators of this problem are supposed to be from renewable sources, meaning PV and wind power. PV and wind power variables are related to their operation, including active and reactive power generated.

The generator constraints are related to:

- Generation curtailment. The active power provided by each renewable generator is positive and limited by the maximum available power from the generation profiles.
- Generator current limits. As generators are connected to the grid through VSCs, they can exchange reactive power. But the total power is limited by a maximum current, which can be expressed similarly to equations (3) and (4) supposing a power factor of 0.915 [12] with respect to the nominal active power of the generator.

2.1.5 Technical and economic indicators

In addition to the previous models, some technical and economic indicators have been defined to analyse the results and set the objective function.

The technical indicators considered are:

- Annual energy losses (E_{loss}) which is expressed as:

$$E_{loss} = \frac{1}{\sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d} \cdot \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot \sum_{t=0}^{23} \sum_{i,k} i_{i,k,t,d}^2 \cdot r_{i,k} \cdot S_b \cdot \Delta t \quad (8)$$

where N_d is the number of representative days, w_d is the weight of each day in the year, $i_{i,k,t,d}$ and $r_{i,k}$ are the current and resistance of the line between bus i and k .

The economic indicators considered are:

- Investment (C_T). This represents the cost of additional equipment installed in the feeders, which mainly considers multiport converter costs (C_{MPC}). Also, costs from other equipment (C_{oth}) can be included, such as the cost of the VSC associated to the PV generators outside the multiport, which is supposed 150 €/kVA.

Figure 1: Electrical scheme of case study

Switches are considered to have zero cost. Then, the total investment cost can be expressed as:

$$C_T = C_{MPC} + C_{oth} \quad (9)$$

- Payback time respect an initial base configuration (PBT). This is the period to recover the initial investment based on additional income from the feeders' operation. Then, the payback time is expressed as:

$$PBT = \frac{\Delta C_T}{C_{loss} \cdot (E_{loss-bc} - E_{loss})} \quad (10)$$

where $E_{loss-bc}$ is the annual losses in the base configuration, and ΔC_T is the increase of total cost with respect to the base configuration. This indicator is especially useful to compare multiport converter solutions or alternative interconnection configurations.

3 Evaluation of multiport converter configurations

Multiport converter configurations are analysed based on the methodology presented in the previous section and considering a case study with different scenarios. The results aim to provide a general conclusion about the application and contribution of multiport converters for voltage support and loss reduction in feeders with distributed generation and high load penetrations.

3.1 Case study

The case study is based on the IEEE 33 bus system [14]. The case study is a 12.66 kV system with one feeder substation, 33 buses and switches in four locations (Fig. 1). These four interconnection options are considered as a possibility to employ a multiport converter instead of a switch.

The network parameters considered for the lines, hourly profiles of load and PV, and load distribution in the buses are taken from [14]. The profiles shown in Fig. 2 are adapted according to the PV power installed or maximum demand in each bus. Generation units correspond to 80% the active power load of the branch buses.

Two generation scenarios have been considered:

- Scenario 1. The PV can only generate active power, and the nominal power of the associated VSC is the same as the nominal power of the PV.

Figure 2: Load and generation profiles

- Scenario 2. The PV can generate both active and reactive power, and the nominal power of the associated VSC is increased to consider a power factor of 0.915 [12] in nominal conditions.

3.2 Configuration definitions

Several configurations are defined based on interconnection locations and MPC options, but also considering direct switch connection.

Two MPC options are considered:

- Two-terminal MPC, similar to a SOP, considering the PV generation is connected to the buses as shown in Fig. 1.
- Three-terminal MPC, considering that the PV generation is connected to the third terminal instead of the buses to which the MPC is connected. Therefore, the MPC between buses 8 and 21 or between 12 and 22 will include the PV of bus 22; the MPC between buses 25 and 29 includes the PV of bus 25; and the MPC between buses 18 and 33 includes the PV of buses 18 and 33.

Moreover, all possible configurations combining MPC and switches are considered for the different locations. Therefore, options from 1 to 4 MPCs will be considered for all locations assuming that remaining locations will have switches, which can be open or closed.

When comparing the different configurations, the increase of total cost refers to the increase of power electronics in the system with respect to the same scenario without multiport converters but considering that the switches of the same interconnections are closed. The annual losses in the base configuration also refer to the losses in the scenario without multiport converters but considering that the switches of the same interconnections are closed. For example, the configuration of a multiport converter between buses 12 and 22 is compared with the configuration of having a closed switch between buses 12 and 22.

3.3 Results and discussion

The results related to the MPC size and location are analysed and compared among the different configurations and scenarios.

Before adding any multiport converter, not all configurations fulfil the requirement of having a minimum voltage of 0.95 p.u. In scenario 1, buses 18 and 33 can reach a minimum voltage of 0.91 p.u., making it is necessary to close

the switches connecting buses 8-21, 12-22 and 25-29 to stay within the voltage limits. Alternatively, if the PV can generate reactive power, as in scenario 2, all switches can remain open without compromising the voltage limit of 0.95 p.u.

In scenario 1 and considering two-terminal MPC, the results show that the best configuration is to mesh the system using most of the available locations. Compared with the switches, the multiport converter can provide reactive power support to increase the voltages and reduce lines' losses. And even if all switches are open, having a single MPC is enough to keep the voltages higher than 0.95 p.u. The best configuration results in a multiport converter interconnecting buses 18 and 33, with switches between buses 8-21, 12-22 and 25-29 (conf. 1). As buses 18 and 33 are the most critical to have undervoltages, the MPC enables to increase their voltage. The size of the MPC in this configuration is 40 kVA for the terminal connecting to bus 18, and 41 kVA for the terminal connecting to bus 33. The second-best configuration consists in an MPC between buses 18-33 and switches between buses 12-22 and 25-29 (conf. 2), where the size of the multiport terminals is 56 and 58 kVA respectively.

Although investment is high, benefits from reduction of system losses must be considered to provide a complete economic evaluation. The payback time is used to consider both investment and losses reduction. For scenario 1 and two-terminal MPC, the paybacks obtained in the best configurations are very high compared with the lifetime of the converter (20-25 years). Therefore, in this case it is not economically feasible to consider multiport converters unless voltage requirements or if the switches can only be closed in emergency situations.

In scenario 2 and considering two-terminal MPC, the optimal configuration includes multiport converters only when all switches remain open. It is preferable to close the switches, if possible, than to have a multiport converter. The best configuration in scenario 2 consists in a multiport converter that interconnects buses 12 and 22 (conf. 3), where each terminal connecting has a nominal power of 278 and 253 kVA, respectively. And the second-best configuration includes a multiport converter between buses 12-22 and 8-21 (conf. 4). In this case, the paybacks obtained from the MPC cost and losses reduction are lower than 20 years (Fig. 4).

In scenario 1 and considering a three-terminal MPC, the optimal configuration results in all PV generators connected to the multiport converters (Fig 3). The best configuration for this case consists in an MPC that connects buses 12-22 with 446 and 390 kVA and a third port for the PV with 46 kW, an MPC between buses 25-29 with 275 and 308 kVA and a third port for the PV with 159 kW, and an MPC that connects buses 18-33 with 229 and 828 kVA and a third port for the PV with 946 kW (conf. 5). This configuration is economically feasible, as the losses reduction compensates the multiport converter costs, resulting in a payback of 12 years. The second-best configuration for this scenario consists in an MPC that connects buses 8-21 with 155 and 139 kVA and a third port for the PV with 288 kW, an MPC between buses 25-29 with 283 and 532 kVA and a third port for the PV with 744 kW, an MPC that connects buses 18-33 with 103 and 332 kVA and a third port for the PV with 385 kW, and

Figure 3: Total converter power for the best configurations

Figure 4: System losses and payback for the best configurations

a closed switch between buses 12-22 (conf. 6). This configuration represents a reduction of power electronics from the base case.

4 Conclusion

This paper analysed the multiport converter as a potential solution to reduce losses in the system lines and avoid undervoltages. A general methodology was presented to size and allocate the required multiport converter based on an optimisation problem with electrical constraints. This methodology also provides technical and economic indicators for a complete evaluation of the multiport converter integration.

The general methodology was validated in a case study based on the IEEE 33 bus system. The results conclude that the multiport converter provides clear advantages and can be economically viable in some cases. In scenarios where the renewable generators can only inject active power, the multiport converter acting as a SOP is located between the buses that would have undervoltages if there was no MPC, although this case is not economically viable. Alternatively, all the generation can be directly connected to multiport converters, resulting in a higher reduction of losses and even reducing the amount of power electronics in the system. In scenarios where the generators can inject both active and reactive power, the multiport acting as a SOP is only recommended to provide additional loss reduction when all switches remain open.

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